

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON ENGLISH COMMUNICATION SKILLS

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Abstract. *The rise of social media has had a significant impact on the way we communicate in English. With the widespread use of platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram, people are constantly exposed to different forms of written and spoken English from around the world. This exposure has led to the phenomenon of "Internet English," where informal language and slang are widely used and accepted. Additionally, social media has made it easier for people to connect and communicate with others, breaking down barriers of language and distance. However, this constant use of social media has also been linked to a decline in traditional English communication skills, such as grammar and spelling. With the ever-evolving landscape of social media, it is important for individuals to be aware of the impact it can have on their English communication skills and to actively work on maintaining and improving them.*

Keywords: *Social media, communication, language skills, media, skills, IT, technologies, tutor, online resources, English skills, idioms, colloquialisms, www, education, universities.*

ВЛИЯНИЕ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ СЕТЕЙ НА АНГЛИЙСКИЙ ЯЗЫК НАВЫКИ КОММУНИКАЦИИ

Аннотация. *Развитие социальных сетей оказало значительное влияние на то, как мы общаемся на английском языке. Благодаря широкому использованию таких платформ, как Facebook, Twitter и Instagram, люди постоянно сталкиваются с различными формами письменного и устного английского языка со всего мира. Это воздействие привело к появлению феномена «интернет-английского», где неформальный язык и сленг широко используются и принимаются. Кроме того, социальные сети облегчили людям общение и общение с другими, разрушая языковые барьеры и расстояния. Однако такое постоянное использование социальных сетей также связано с ухудшением традиционных навыков английского общения, таких как грамматика и правописание. В условиях постоянно меняющегося ландшафта социальных сетей людям важно осознавать, какое влияние они могут оказать на их навыки общения на английском языке, и активно работать над их поддержанием и улучшением.*

Ключевые слова: *социальные сети, общение, языковые навыки, средства массовой информации, навыки, ИТ, технологии, репетитор, онлайн-ресурсы, навыки английского языка, идиомы, разговорные выражения, www, образование, университеты.*

As the world becomes more interconnected, the English language has emerged as the global lingua franca, enabling people from different cultures and countries to communicate effectively. With the advent of social media platforms, such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and Snapchat,

the way we communicate in English has experienced a significant transformation. These platforms have undoubtedly influenced our English communication skills, both positively and negatively.

One of the positive aspects of social media's influence on English communication skills is the democratization of language learning. In the past, learning English required attending formal classes or hiring a tutor. However, now anyone with internet access can learn English through online resources, language exchange programs, and engaging with native speakers on social media platforms. This accessibility has made it easier for people all over the world to improve their English skills and communicate effectively in a global context. Moreover, social media platforms have provided a space for individuals to practice their English communication skills in a real-world context. Through interactions on social media, users are exposed to a wide range of English language expressions, idioms, and colloquialisms. This exposure helps users become more familiar with the nuances of the language and develop a more natural and authentic way of communicating in English. Additionally, social media has encouraged users to express themselves creatively, thus enhancing their language proficiency.

This research shows how social media has affected learning at present during the COVID-19 pandemic and how it has become the largest and most convenient area of communication. In the current scenario, it seems that social networking sites not only had a profound impact on our social structure and intra-social interaction, but also affected education in general and learning English language in particular. It has been proven that these various social media platforms have created a realm of digital environment in today's new-age learning. Social media platforms are social networking sites through which people interact and communicate with each other easily and conveniently. Undoubtedly and unquestionably, social networking has been proven to be a global phenomenon that has caused a vast paradigm shift in the world of Learning and education during the current pandemic. Therefore, the present study aims to reach the extent of the impact of the various social media platforms on learning English language during the COVID-19 pandemic from the students' point of view.

Design/methodology/approach

The study was conducted at the undergraduate level for English language learners. The sample comprised 166 undergraduate students at Najran University. A survey questionnaire was administered to find out the impact of various social media platforms and social networking sites on learning English language in the academic year of 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic and to highlight possible suggestions for improving future virtual language learning.

Findings

The findings of the study contributed to the area of online learning of English language during the COVID-19 pandemic. Final results confirmed that the utilization of social media has been significantly perceived to have positively impacted learning English language in terms of writing style, reading skills, listening and lexical variation, communication skills and grammar usage.

Practical implications

The findings of the study can serve as fundamental indicators to implement prompt pedagogical reformations, for which a number of pedagogical implications can be proposed. Another equally important pedagogical implication is to design and provide professional

development and training sessions to both students and educators on the ultimate utilization of social media as instructional technologies in the context of English language teaching and learning.

This research provides insights in developing policies to assist with the integration and utilization of social media platforms as instructional technologies in the context of English language teaching and learning and how institutions can respond to the advent of advancing technology, especially during and after the COVID-19 era. A model to improve online English language learning process is recommended as a guideline for all educators offering online learning.

In our increasingly interconnected world, the ability to effectively communicate in English has become a crucial skill for individuals across all walks of life. English has emerged as the global language of business, education, and international relations, making it essential for people to develop strong English communication skills to thrive in today's globalized society.

Firstly, English communication skills are vital for career advancement. In many industries, the ability to communicate fluently in English is considered a basic requirement. Employers value candidates who can effectively interact with colleagues and clients from different countries and cultural backgrounds. Strong English communication skills open up a world of opportunities, allowing professionals to work in multinational corporations, engage in international projects, and explore job prospects in different countries. Furthermore, English proficiency is often associated with higher salary potential and increased career growth opportunities.

Students are more engaged in learning when they have access to media in the classroom. Media can help illustrate a lesson by allowing students to see real-life examples of what they're learning. Smart Boards and other interactive media allow students to move objects on a screen for illustrative purposes.

Connectivity is among the most significant benefits of social media. It can link countless users at any time, everywhere. Information could be spread globally through social media and its connectedness, making it simple for people to interact with one another. It results in global relationships.

Beyond the professional sphere, English communication skills also play a significant role in academic pursuits. Many renowned universities and educational institutions worldwide offer courses taught in English. Whether it is pursuing higher education or participating in academic conferences, a solid command of the English language is essential for students to fully engage and excel in these academic environments. Moreover, English proficiency is a key requirement for studying abroad, allowing students to experience different cultures, broaden their horizons, and gain an international perspective. English communication skills are not limited to career and academics; they also enhance personal growth and cultural understanding. English is the language of literature, music, cinema, and popular culture. By having a good command of the language, individuals gain access to a wealth of resources, allowing them to appreciate and understand different cultures, traditions, and perspectives. Additionally, effective English communication skills enable individuals to connect with people from diverse backgrounds, fostering cross-cultural understanding and empathy.

Language changes simply because the needs of its speakers change. With the rise of social media, people also require new words to communicate in a way that's more suited to modern times. So with the arrival of various social media sites.

Social media provides real life language and models how native speakers actually interact with each other. Teacher can suggest the students keep the unfamiliar vocabulary or structure they find on social media sites to discuss in class. Fourthly, encourage students to interact with each other in class and online.

The role of social media in English language writing development is like the brightness of the day because social media facilitate the English learners to learn new words and phrases and to improve their writing skills.

You can use them in the following ways:

Building a class blog, where students can take it in turns to write posts on topics of interest. Other students can then add comments. ...

Creating lessons based on blogs. ...

Having students start their own blogs.

The English language's social purpose is to unite people, help them communicate and understand each other, and provide a link between cultures. One of the most commonly spoken languages on the planet is English. More than 400 million individuals, both native and second-language speakers, use it.

Effective English language and communication skills are crucial in many aspects of life, including education, business, diplomacy, travel, and social interactions. Proficient English language skills enable individuals to express themselves clearly, understand others, and engage in meaningful conversations.

Social media addiction has been linked to increased stress, anxiety, and depression, with detrimental effects on the learning process. Students who are distracted by social media may struggle to stay engaged in class, miss important information or assignments, and experience decreased academic performance as a result.

However, social media use can also negatively affect teens, distracting them, disrupting their sleep, and exposing them to bullying, rumor spreading, unrealistic views of other people's lives and peer pressure. The risks might be related to how much social media teens use.

On the other hand, social media's influence on English communication skills has also brought about some negative consequences. One of the most prominent issues is the rise of abbreviations, acronyms, and emojis. While these forms of communication are convenient and help convey emotions succinctly, they can undermine the development of proper English language skills. Overuse of abbreviations and acronyms may lead to a deterioration of grammar, punctuation, and spelling. Additionally, reliance on emojis can diminish the ability to express complex emotions or convey ideas effectively through words. Moreover, critics argue that social media has diminished face-to-face communication skills. As individuals spend more time interacting through screens, they may struggle with the nuances of non-verbal cues, body language, and vocal intonations. Consequently, this could hinder their ability to communicate effectively in real-life situations, such as job interviews, negotiations, or public speaking engagements.

Despite the potential drawbacks, the influence of social media on English communication skills is undeniable. It has revolutionized the way we learn, practice, and use English in our everyday lives. Therefore, it is essential to strike a balance between utilizing social media as a tool for language improvement and recognizing its limitations.

To make the most of social media's influence on English communication skills, individuals should adopt a proactive approach. They should actively seek out reputable online resources, engage in meaningful conversations with native speakers, and participate in language exchange programs. Additionally, it is crucial to maintain a balance between online and offline interactions, ensuring that face-to-face communication skills are not neglected.

In conclusion, social media platforms have had a profound influence on English communication skills. While they have democratized language learning and provided opportunities for creative expression, they have also introduced potential pitfalls, such as over-reliance on abbreviations and diminished face-to-face communication skills. By leveraging the positive aspects of social media while remaining mindful of its limitations, individuals can enhance their English communication skills and navigate the globalized world with confidence.

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